

Designing the VR Probe: An Introductory Application to Virtual Reality for People Living with Dementia (PLWD)

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Abstract

Dementia is a condition which involves a gradual degradation of cognitive functioning over time. The number of people living with dementia (PLWD) is increasing every year. The use of Virtual Reality (VR) in health related research has gained popularity, in part due to the availability of VR headsets such as the Oculus Quest and the HTC Vive and the immersive nature of VR. VR interventions are recognised as having great potential for PLWD. To ensure effective VR based experiments involving PLWD, it is critical to introduce this audience to VR. While there are commercially available introduction applications, none have been designed with PLWD in mind. This paper describes the design considerations made for a VR Probe application having a dual purpose: to introduce PLWD to VR and to help inform design decisions for future VR applications. This paper also describes the technological implementation decisions for a replicable VR environment such as task design, interaction system, multisensory design and virtual representation.

Keywords: Virtual Reality, Older Adults, Dementia, Immersion, Simulation

1 Introduction

Virtual Reality (VR) is a form of technology that uses a head mounted display (HMD) to display an artificial 3D environment, utilising a combination of visual, audio and in some cases haptic feedback to provide an immersive experience to the user [Gigante, 1993]. Research using VR has increased due to the greater accessibility of HMD technology, with one such area of research being the use of VR for people living with dementia (PLWD).

Dementia is a neurodegenerative condition which leads to a gradual decline in cognitive functioning over time [WHO, 2020]. Globally, over 55 million people have been diagnosed with dementia, with 10 million new people being diagnosed every year [WHO, 2020]. While currently there is no cure for dementia [WHO, 2020], research has found that non-pharmacological activities (e.g. reminiscence therapy and light exercise) can help to enrich the lives of PLWD [Shigihara et al., 2020]. Furthermore, studies show that technology (e.g. VR) provides opportunities to support PLWD from assessment, to monitoring to the support of cognitive and physical functioning [Astell et al., 2019]. Examples of VR interventions include: the use of adaptive music therapy to reduce negative emotions and increase memory performance in PLWD [Byrns et al., 2020] and the use of VR for ‘light’ physical activities (e.g. virtual bowling) to support PLWD in recalling motor tasks [Fenney and Lee, 2010]. The capability of VR interventions to provide old and new experiences for PLWD without the difficulties of travel [Möhler et al., 2020] has become increasingly important after identifying PLWD’s heightened feelings of isolation as a result of the Covid-19 restrictions in 2020 [Curelaru et al., 2021].

As 91% of PLWD are diagnosed after the age of 65 years [WHO, 2020], PLWD who are being involved in VR research likely have no prior experience using the technology [Flynn et al., 2022b]. As such, there is a need to introduce them to VR as part of the research process. While there are commercially available VR introduction applications such as ‘First Steps’ or ‘First Contact’ developed by Oculus, these applications are designed for a general audience and do not contain effective design considerations for older adults [Abeele et al., 2021].

This paper describes the design decisions of a VR probe: an application to introduce PLWD to VR and its basic functionality. This paper aims to describe the technical implementation and development considerations for the VR probe. Gaver et al (1999) defines a cultural probe as a design led approach to research where participants are shown design artefacts to promote ideas and discussion between participants and researchers to gain a better understanding of the research field and promote new design ideas [Gaver et al., 1999]. The aim of this probe is to ensure that such PLWD would be able to experience VR to better inform design decisions for future VR applications [Hutchinson et al., 2003].

2 System Architecture

The VR probe was created using the Unity3D game engine. This engine was chosen due to its popularity for creating cross platform 2D and 3D environments [González et al., 2017]. Unity also supports the creation of VR applications through its XR Interaction Toolkit [Unity3D, 2023]. Using the XRRig object provided by this toolkit allowed a quick implementation of the user's virtual representation as a part of a VR setting. The VR probe environment was created using a living room model developed in LiveHome2D which was then imported into Unity. Unity3D uses the toolkit's interaction system to manage interactions between virtual objects and the user. The probe environment was designed to function on the Oculus Quest 2 HMD as the device can run the application without being connected to a computer. This was important as the portability of the Oculus Quest 2 allows it to be easily used by PLWD regardless of where they are situated (e.g. sitting on a chair, in bed, etc [Saredakis et al., 2021]), and can be applied in home or healthcare settings.

3 Task Design

The Responsive, Engaging, Augmenting, Failure-Free (REAFF) framework defines a set of principles to guide the design of technology to support PLWD [Astell, 2009]. With this framework in mind, several tasks were developed for the VR probe to reflect common actions within VR. These tasks consisted of; (1) selection - where the participant is required to select one of the three cubes on the table (Figure 1) using the controller, (2) object placement - where the participant is required to use the controller to pick up the ball on the table and place it within the container on the table (Figure 2), (3) gaze - where the participant is required to look at a screen and watch a video until it has concluded (Figure 3), and (4) teleportation - where the participant is instructed to direct the controller to a specified point on the ground and press the trigger button to move to that point (Figure 5). To promote autonomy in PLWD and in line with the REAFF guidelines, the tasks were designed with simple functionality and flexibility in mind (i.e. each task was designed for easy completion: all tasks could be completed in no particular order [Hutchinson et al., 2003]). The tasks were developed by placing game objects within the environment and then attaching interactable components which allowed these objects to be picked up or interacted with by the player. Components were also attached to the objects to call an event when the task was completed.

Figure 1: Selection Task

Figure 1: Object Placement Task

Figure 3: Gaze Task

When a participant approaches a task, a user interface (UI) panel appears displaying task instructions. This is in line with Braley et al. (2018) who suggested that the use of prompting in technology can improve the functional independence of PLWD [Braley et al., 2018]. When the task completion event is called, the UI panel changes to an encouraging message (Figure 4) as studies show that PLWD respond faster to positive feedback [Maki et al., 2018]. The foreground and background colours were specifically selected to provide appropriate visual contrast [McIntyre et al., 2019].

Figure 4: Encouraging Message on the UI panel

4 Interaction and Locomotion

All Interaction and locomotion decisions relating to the VR probe were underpinned by the fact that a higher level of interaction fidelity can lead to a greater sense of immersion within the virtual environment [Rogers et al., 2019]. To avoid physical strain on the PLWD participants as they interacted with the virtual environment (e.g. picking up objects similar to how they would do so in the real world using the provided controllers), interaction rays were added to the hands to allow objects to be grabbed from a distance. This is in line with findings by Argelaguet and Andujar (2013) who identified raycasting selection as one of the most popular techniques for its effectiveness and ease of use [Argelaguet and Andujar, 2013]. The interaction rays point out from the hands and highlight when an object is interactable (Figure 5). To reduce the cognitive load of having to memorise different buttons and associated actions, the trigger button is assigned to grabbing, teleporting and interaction actions. An extra interaction ray, attached to the virtual head triggers gaze interactions when the participant looks at the video-screen virtual object (Figure 3).

As locomotion in VR allows participants to move their virtual representation in the VR space [Bozgeyikli et al., 2016], this enables the creation of larger VR environments that are not limited to the boundary set by the HMD. The most common forms of VR locomotion are joystick movement and teleportation [Buttussi and Chittaro, 2021], however other methods such as arm cycling have also been developed [Coomer et al., 2018]. As joystick movement can cause cybersickness and arm-cycling is tiring for participants, we integrated teleportation into the VR probe for its ease of use. [Coomer et al., 2018]. Teleportation anchor points were placed beside each task space, so that once participants pointed their hand rays at the red squares and pressed the trigger button, they would be instantaneously transported to that location. The teleportation anchors change colour once the interaction ray hovers over them, in order to inform the participant to which position they can teleport (Figure 5). The teleportation anchors contain components to detect interactions from a teleportation provider component attached to the XRRig.

Figure 5: Teleportation visual cues

5 Multisensory Design

VR can be utilised to provide a multisensory, immersive experience for participants which can lead to a more meaningful time in the virtual world [Abeele et al., 2021]. The combination of visual, audio and haptic stimuli can provide a greater sense of immersion [Muñoz et al., 2022]. Furthermore, the use of multisensory VR design supports participants with impaired senses (i.e. cognitive and/or physical) [Hodge et al., 2018]. Within the context of the VR probe, the video component of the gaze task (Figure 3) provides both visual and audio stimuli to the participants. Furthermore, as the participant hovers over interactable objects, an event is called which adds a distinctly coloured outline or changes the material colour (Figures 1 and 2). The interaction rays also change colour as they hover over the interactable objects. In addition to the visual changes, the controllers vibrate during the hovering event. Through the use of both visual and haptic feedback, the participant is informed of the interactable nature of the object through pressing the trigger button. This haptic feedback is alongside visual cues (Figure 5) which indicate to the participant the place to which they can teleport.

6 Virtual Representation

A virtual avatar is a visual representation of the participant while they are inside the VR environment [Hodge et al., 2018]. Avatars can have full bodies, half bodies or virtual hands. Studies showed that for younger adults, the inclusion of an avatar can improve performance in cognitive tasks regardless of the type of avatar used [Pan and Steed, 2019]. PLWD are able to accept the presence of virtual hands as their own while they are using VR [Matsangidou et al., 2020]. Mendez et al. (2015) demonstrated that PLWD can accept the presence of other virtual avatars within their virtual environment [Mendez et al., 2015]. In the VR probe, a full body avatar was initially used (Figure 6). However, prior to testing on PLWD, the use of a full body avatar was found to cause disembodiment due to the inconsistency in movement between the virtual and physical forearms. As a result, virtual hands were chosen as they move consistently with the controllers (Figure 7). Hand models were downloaded from the Oculus Developer website and attached to the hand interactors on the XRRig. Animator components were also added to add realism to object grabbing interactions, by changing the pose of the hands when the participants held the trigger button.

Figure 6: Full Body Avatar

Figure 7: Virtual Hands

7 Contributions to Research

Underpinned by an extensive literature review and in collaboration with an occupational therapist, a VR probe was designed, developed and tested by nine PLWD, along with their care-givers. While previous VR studies involving PLWD have mentioned the technology which was used, they rarely go into sufficient technical detail for other researchers to replicate the experimental environment for further research. This paper describes the design and implementation decisions which scaffolded the VR probe and which can be replicated by future researchers. Note: The VR probe was used in a study which introduced PLWD and their care-givers to VR [Flynn et al., 2022a]. The findings from this study were used to further refine the probe e.g. implementing graphical anti-aliasing to ensure that the graphics appeared smoother, and including background audio to improve the sense of realism within the virtual environment.

8 Future Work

This paper details the design and technical implementation decisions for a VR probe for PLWD. Feedback from the use of this probe as outlined in [Flynn et al., 2022a] can be used to inform the design of future VR applications for PLWD. As the design and technical implementation considerations of the VR probe were made with older PLWD in mind, this probe can also be used to introduce older adults without dementia to VR. It should be noted that gameplay based data was not gathered during the probe's testing period as its primary purpose was to introduce PLWD to VR. However, future uses of the VR probe will include both quantitative (i.e. game play data) and qualitative (e.g. interview) data in order to gain more specific insight into how PLWD both navigate VR environments and engage with task based VR activities.

9 Conclusion

With the number of dementia diagnoses increasing every year, the need for effective interventions to improve the quality of life for PLWD is becoming more necessary. While VR has proven to be an effective tool for non-pharmacological interventions, it is clear that PLWD need an appropriate introduction to VR. This paper described the design considerations underpinning the VR probe for introducing PLWD to VR within the context of interaction, locomotion and immersion. In addition to outlining the underpinning design considerations, this paper also presented the technology architecture and implementation decisions of the VR probe.

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